

Study of Quantitative Indicators of Engineering Machinery Reliability

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***Abstract:** The efficiency of using engineering machines will depend on numerous parameters and indicators characterizing the operational properties of the machines and their influence on the reliability of the equipment.*

The article presents the results of a study of reliability indicators of a single-bucket excavator of the KrAZ-255 EOY-4421 brand during use and effective operation, as well as quantitative characteristics of indicators of effective use of the excavator.

***Key words:** engineering vehicles, reliability, operating time, excavator, process, cutting parts, effect, durability, safety, stability.*

Introduction

Reliability is one of the characteristics of the machine. It is very specific, as it depends on random factors; Some specific characteristics are identified; its experimental research is associated with difficulties than the study of other technical characteristics (with a greater expenditure of time, material resources, and the labor of qualified specialists).

When studying reliability, research and testing of individual parts, assemblies, machines as a whole and machine systems are carried out, which in reliability theory are called objects. Each object is designed to perform certain functions established by technical documentation, standards, technical conditions, and is characterized by operational indicators, which are called output parameters. Acceptable values of output parameters are established by technical documentation [1].

Research into increasing the efficiency of using road-building machines, including single-bucket excavators, by improving and increasing the operational reliability indicators of machines, taking into account the factors influencing their operational reliability indicators in extreme operating conditions, is a very urgent task [2].

Methods

It is known that the efficiency of using road construction machines will increase from a large number of parameters and indicators characterizing the operational properties of the machines and their influence on the reliability of the equipment.

The operational indicators of reliability and durability of the main components and assemblies and, in general, machines that ensure the safe operation of machines, both in operating mode and in transport mode, operating at high temperatures must be no lower than the established requirements imposed by firms, companies and manufacturers [3].

Thus, based on the research results obtained, it is necessary to develop technological and technical-operational recommendations and proposals for a single-bucket excavator intended for operation in hot climates, as well as in sharply continental and high-mountainous areas.

Further, to solve the research problems, a methodology was developed to determine the operational reliability indicators of a single-bucket excavator of the KrAZ-255 EOV-4421 brand, such as: time between failures, a failure flow parameter, as well as gamma-percentage resources of parts and assemblies limiting the reliability of a single-bucket excavator [4].

Planning for operational repairs taking into account the working capital of units and assembly units, as well as the availability of posts for carrying out repairs of a specific enterprise, in order to reduce abnormal machine downtime during operational repairs due to machine failure.

Results

The failure rate parameter of the KrAZ-255 EOV-4421 single-bucket excavator is presented in Table 1.

Excavator Brand Failure Flow Parameter
“KrAZ-255 EOV-4421”

Table 1.

№	Operating intervals	Number of cars observed in a given interval N_j	Number of failures for all machines in a given interval m_j	Average number of failures per d_j machine	Failure flow parameter λ_j
1	0-250	6	12	1.90	0.0086
2	251-500	7	9	1.42	0.0057
3	501-750	5	8	1.79	0.0071
4	751-1000	6	8	1.60	0.0059
5	1001-1250	4	5	1.44	0.0058
6	1251-1500	4	6	1.77	0.0069
7	1501-1750	6	7	1.31	0.0051
8	1751-2000	6	9	1.70	0.0071
9	2001-2250	7	10	1.65	0.0069
10	2251-2500	5	8	2.98	0.0076
11	2501-2750	6	9	1.72	0.0074
12	2751-3000	6	8	1.33	0.0053

The graph of the failure flow parameter for the KrAZ-255 EOV-4421 excavator is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Excavator failure flow parameter graph brand "KrAZ-255 EOV-4421".

Conditional on 80% and 90% gamma percentage resources of parts and assemblies is a regulated probability that characterizes the probability of maintaining the operability of machines.

As a result of a study of the operational reliability indicators of a single-bucket excavator, specific values of machine operating time are determined, which is based on the average service life of parts and machine assemblies [5].

Based on the results of the study, 80% and 90% gamma-percentage resources of parts and assemblies limiting the reliability of the KrAZ-255 EOV-4421 single-bucket excavator were determined and established.

It has been established that the significantly minimum gamma-percentage resource of parts and assemblies, limiting the reliability of the single-bucket excavator of the KrAZ-255 EOV-4421 brand, is the rubber parts (cuffs, seals and rubber rings) of the hydraulic system of the machines, namely the 80 x 115 cuff of the boom hydraulic cylinder working equipment.

Determination of 80% and 90% resources of the 80x115 cuff of the KrAZ-255 EOV-4421 excavator is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Determination of 80% and 90% resources of the cuff 80x115 excavator "KrAZ-255 EOY-4421".

Discussion

It can be seen from Fig. 2. that 80% and 90% resources of the cuff 80 x 115 limiting the reliability of the hydraulic cylinder unit of the boom of a single-bucket excavator of the KrAZ-255 EOY-4421 brand are respectively: m/h and motor-hour, these resources are also the resource life of the hydraulic cylinder arrows in general [6].

As a result of the research, the values of 80% and 90% gamma-percent resources of the part that limits the reliability of the undercarriage of the KrAZ-255 EOY-4421 single-bucket excavator, which is the crosspiece of connecting bridges and cardan shafts, were also determined and established. One of the main reasons for the failure of the crosspiece is the acceleration of the wear process from transport relocation from one object to another, as well as from inertial load during the work process [7].

The established values of the gamma-percentage resources of the crosspiece of a single-bucket excavator of the KrAZ-255 EOY-4421 brand connecting the axles and cardan shafts, respectively, are: $T_{p80} = 1930.0$ m/h, $T_{p90} = 1346.0$ m/h.

Conclusion

As a result of the research, values of 80% and 90% gamma-percentage resources of parts and assemblies of limiting reliability of the single-bucket excavator of the KrAZ-255 EOY-4421 brand were obtained, which will allow rationing spare parts and their costs, as well as planning the costs of these parts and units in the future.

Based on the results obtained, proposals and recommendations are being developed to improve the design of a single-bucket excavator, adapted for operation in hot climates.

For rubber seals, it is recommended to use heat-resistant rubber or multi-edge rubber sealing parts, namely: cuffs, oil seals and others in the hydraulic system of a single-bucket excavator of the KrAZ-255 EOY-4421 brand.

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